

The effects of Using Blended Learning Approach in English Language Teaching and Learning: A literature Review

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Abstract: The development of technology has helped a lot in teaching and learning English. Technology can be a tool to help the teacher of English facilitate language learning. There are many aspects of using technology in teaching but, Blended Learning (BL) approach has become a matter of interest to language teachers all over the world. Blended Learning combines the traditional face-to-face teaching and online teaching. It rests on the strengths of both teaching approaches. This study provides a comprehensive review of relevant literature on the use of Blended Learning in teaching and learning English. Moreover, it focuses on the use of technology in general and specifically on Blended Learning approach, its models, tools and advantages. The literature highlighted great benefits of Blended Learning on learning and teaching in general and specifically on English learning and teaching.

Keywords: Technology, Blended learning, E-learning, Teaching and Learning English, Language skills.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of modern technology in teaching English has become indispensable, especially with the great revolution of advanced technology in all fields and sectors. Modern technology such as the Internet, computers, laptops smartphones and others are used widely in teaching English nowadays to facilitate applying new methods and techniques in teaching that lead to the achievement of the desired goals of teaching. Using technology in English language teaching improves learners' language skills and develops efficient teaching and learning. One of the ultimate goals of using modern technology in teaching English is to maximize learners' skills in English and to actively engage learners in the language learning. Integrating technology in teaching English for adults' learners may increase language learning opportunities.

A lot of approaches were experimented and each approach has its benefits and challenges. The new trend approach in education which has been a controversial subject is the "Blended Learning approach". To get the ultimate benefits of teaching and to help learners achieve effective integration of online and face-to-face learning, Blended Learning which is a hybrid teaching model emerged. This approach of teaching depends on combining the traditional face-to-face method with using technology. It combines two models to reach the most effective and efficient methods to achieve the learning goals. It combines the benefits of both models. Face-to-face instruction offers the benefit of fluid, real-time interaction with instructors and peers with the advantage of immediate assistance, collaboration, and feedback, but is confined to a set time and place. Online learning offers time and space flexibility, allows more individualized instruction, but it may lack face-to-face instructor and learner communication. A Blended Learning method blends the benefits of the two instructions and at the same time diminishes the constraints. This approach is considered a systematic method that integrates the benefits of the traditional face-to-face instruction and online interaction. Blended learning may solve some issues regarding transportation distances and building costs that could arise with traditional face-to-face instruction.

Blended Learning approach is increasingly used nowadays by various educational administrations to create new teaching methodology that combines e-learning with the traditional classroom methods. In fact, Blended Learning provides English Language learners with different interactive language activities since it integrates face-to-face education and technology-based education. Blended Learning is an innovative teaching method that offers students with a flexible teaching environment.

Blended Learning is a new teaching method that considers teachers as information providers; and learners as seekers for information. Blended Learning emerged to develop the learning system and to encourage teachers to be more practical and change their teaching methods constantly since it includes online teaching which provides uncountable sources of educational materials available for teachers. Since that face-to-face teaching may not be enough to serve all the learners' requirements, this will lead to the need for online learning to be used in parallel with face-to-face learning to have a successful learning process. Distinguished instructors employ different teaching methods to foster each student's learning abilities.

When using Blended Learning, instructors can adapt and edit the online course materials in a way that suits the learners' needs and the course learning goals. Also, blending two types of teaching methods offers more opportunities for instructors to use different effective teaching methods. In addition, they can upload various activities and they can ask their learners to get online sessions and to upload their written material. Blended Learning provides language learners the opportunity to learn the authentically. It is a considered student-centred method. By using this teaching method, learners can easily access the learning materials anytime and everywhere. Also, it allows practicing the teaching and learning activities inside and outside the classroom. So, learners can benefit from this learning method in terms of time and place. Learners could specify the suitable time and place to complete the recommended educational activities which will be of a great motivation for them.

In contrast to the traditional learning environment that is restricted by place and time, online learning offers learners a flexible learning environment where they can study anytime anywhere. By using this method, learners have the chance to practice the language in the classroom with their peers and with a lecturer and then at home they can adjust their time to learn using their laptops and the Internet. It extends the learning process outside the classroom by accessing through the learning resources. Moreover, it makes online course available to other countries' learners. Furthermore, with Blended Learning approach, learners will be in contact with their teachers inside and outside the classroom which will improve the learning process. Blended learning provides an opportunity for the learners to practice the language through online platforms such as video-conferencing. This will help achieve the ultimate benefits of learning a language.

The Blended Learning approach has been used to overcome the obstacles in the traditional learning; with the shortage in the educational budgets, in teachers, and the increasing English language learners, the need for a good-quality instruction is becoming increasingly important. It is the online component that becomes a natural extension of traditional classroom learning. So, it is considered a powerful solution to improve language learning experience. It was noticeable that Blended Learning insures better academic performance compared with the type of learning that delivered only online.

The Blended Learning method provides great benefits of mixing learning environments. It combines lectures, workshops, autonomy learning and interactive exercises that simulate the use of interactive multimedia. It combines classroom face-to-face teaching with and online interactive techniques. Blended learning joins elements of e-learning such as online discussions into traditional classroom. Using Blended Learning improves the learning activities such as including discussion, online quizzes and assignments. Instructors can apply different face-to-face activities in a Blended-Learning system by using various digital tools. This will promote the learners to practice the language outside the class and will improve their language skills. Blended Learning combines the online learning with classroom interaction and live instruction in a way that helps in personalizing the process of learning.

Blended learning helps learners work individually and interact with others online. This will help to develop learner's autonomy. Working individually enhances different types of skills such as the skills of managing, researching, and developing. With Blended Learning, learners will be able to realize their own points of strengths and weaknesses, and this will help them to carry out the process of learning outside the classroom through online learning. This will lead instructors to deal with different educational factors such as learners' different personalities, their individual differences, and with the variety of learning styles. For instance, shy learners will find it easier to communicate online than communicating face-to-face with others in the classroom.

Online learning provides learners the chance to practice more since, it is accessible nearly 24 hours. In this environment, the teacher plays different roles: a facilitator, observant, and supervisor. He facilitates the way to use online materials for the students; He checks learners' mistakes and corrects them immediately; and he supervises the learners' language development.

The term "Blended Learning" is considered a new term in the field of education. It was designed to join between the most effective and efficient modes of learning. In other words, blended learning joins between two forms of learning: the traditional classroom face-to-face learning and the online learning. This will help learners to use higher levels of thinking skills.

Online learning is described as anywhere anytime learning, since learners can participate in the learning activities outside the classroom anytime anywhere. It emphasizes on the continuous interaction between the learners and their teacher.

Blended Learning brings the benefits of online instruction as it provides a wide range of varied educational materials that can be practiced outside the classroom.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Effects of Blended Learning Approach on English Teaching and Learning

Over the past few years, many studies have searched the advantages of implementing the Blended Learning method in English language teaching and learning. It is considered one teaching approaches that enhances self-learning. Recent researches have recommended the use of Blended Learning due to its social and academic benefits since, it depends on the strengths of both the traditional teaching method and the online or distance method.

Many studies that have been done on Blended Learning and the implementing online learning into face-to-face learning. Most of these studies emphasize on the integration between technology and learning. It has been shown that Blended Learning approach helps in improving the teaching and learning process. It is a way to apply technology in the teaching and learning English to empower the level of education.

Some studies about Blended Learning were applied on teachers. Siew-Eng & Muuk (2015) searched the reason why teachers of English use Blended Learning and what type of tools used by them in Blended Learning. The researchers revealed ten reasons why teachers of English use the method of Blended Learning: it supports face-to-face teaching approach, it supports collaboration, it eases communication through social networking, it increases accessibility of learning materials, it reduces class time, it creates interesting lesson, it creates a student-centred learning environment, it creates motivating learning environment, it is flexible (learning time and location) and it develops independent learning skills. In addition, the study mentioned some tools used by English teachers: PowerPoint, audio files, email, social networking sites, laptops, tablet PCs, and mobile phones.

A similar study by Ju & Mei (2018) who investigated perception of foreign language instructors in Blended Learning teaching. The participants were foreign language teachers. A interviews and questionnaire were used as instruments. It was found that instructors showed positive perceptions towards Blended Learning. The instructors have mentioned that their personal proficiency in technology and ICT application are necessary to guarantee an effective and productive blended teaching and learning. In another study about English teachers, Ekayati (2019) investigated teachers' perception on Blended Learning model in teaching English at State Vocational School assisted by Edmodo. The study included 10 English teachers. Data collected was collected from questionnaires, observation, and direct interview. The result showed that instructors of English expressed positive perception towards using Edmodo in Blended Learning model. It also showed that this could help in solving issues in teaching English in the class.

Some studies showed a relation between Blended Learning and comprehending grammar. Chansamrong, Tubsree, & Kiratibodee (2014) studied the effectiveness of Blended Learning and cooperative learning to teach grammar in Thailand. The participants were 100 students separated in two different groups. A pre-test and a post-test and a survey were given. The results revealed that both the above and under average students showed a better score after studying grammar through the blended-cooperative learning. The results also showed that most of the participants had good attitudes about using Blended Learning for learning English grammar.

Similar results can be found in a study done Şahin-Kızıl (2014) who investigated learners' perceptions of Blended Learning in tertiary institutions. The study consisted of sixty-eight university students. A questionnaire was used as the study instrument. The results revealed that having an effective learning can be accomplished when combining the

traditional interactions with Moodle interventions. Using Moodle may help in developing learners' grammar and reading comprehension. Moreover, it showed that blended language course can enhance students' satisfaction with the course. Another study that showed a relation between Blended Learning and grammar was presented by Isti'annah (2017) who has studied the effect of using Blended Learning on learners in a grammar class. The participants were 26 learners from English department at Sanata Dharma University. A pre-test, a post-test, a questionnaire and students' reflective journal were given. The results were consistent with other studies in this regard. The findings of the study have revealed that using Blended Learning in teaching English grammar was effective. Moreover, most of the learners have found that using online activities has helped them a lot in comprehending the materials. Also, the study has showed that implementing the Blended Learning method in teaching English grammar enhanced the learners' interest in learning English grammar.

Similar results were found in a study about learners' perceptions and attitudes towards using Blended Learning in teaching EFL, Ja'ashan (2015) employed a survey on a group of English learners. The results of the data showed the learners' positive attitudes towards the use of Blended Learning in the English course. The students showed high satisfaction with the approach of Blended Learning as it enhanced their English language skills and helped them make English learning collaborative, interactive and interesting. Therefore, Blended Learning is an effective method in improving autonomous learning and in increasing students' motivation. As many studies concluded, to achieve an affective Blended Learning method, learners should have positive attitudes and a positive technology experience.

Similarly, Akbarov, Gönen & Aydoğan (2018) studied the attitudes of EFL learners towards Blended Learning. A questionnaire was employed on a group of learners to measure their attitudes towards Blended Learning approach. The findings of the study showed that most of the EFL learners had positive attitudes towards Blended Learning. The participants preferred using this approach in learning English as it helps in enhancing their motivation to learn English and it improves their English proficiency levels. The study concluded that the approach of Blended Learning is considered a valuable method that helps to reach the ultimate benefits of English teaching and learning.

Some studies showed the effects of Blended Learning in higher education. Abdul Rahman, Hussein & Aluwi (2015) studied the satisfaction of Blended Learning in a public higher education institution. Students of a public higher education institution have participated in questionnaires. The study concluded that Blended Learning may improve the quality of learning by providing learners better platforms.

This means that effective education can be achieved when blending the advantages of a web environment with face-to-face interaction in courses that require using visual elements. This will achieve student-centred learning. These findings agree with the findings of a study by Zhang & Zhu (2018) who compared learning outcomes of Blended Learning and traditional Learning of University Students in ESL Courses. The study showed that the group of learners who were taught through Blended Learning approach had better academic performance in ESL course than the group of learners who were taught through the traditional approach. The results indicated that the use of Blended Learning approach had a positive impact on the learners' learning outcomes. The researchers stated that Blended Learning is an initial teaching and learning factor for higher education. It provides learners with different types of skills. Blended Learning is becoming an interest for higher education learners, since it requires using the internet and computer-techniques which are of a big interest for young people.

All the results of the mentioned studies ensure the effectiveness of blending the advantages of the traditional face-to-face instruction and online learning. Many educators think that this blend will make teaching and learning English meaningful. Blended Learning help learners to choose the suitable learning methods. It increases the learners' interest in learning, it prepares them for future life and they will gain several skills such as computer literacy, self-learning skills, research skills, and self-engagement skills.

Generally, several studies proved that Blended Learning helps instructors improve the teaching conditions; Also, it offers instructors access to a variety of resources and materials that suit learners' level of knowledge and interest; It also helps instructors to improve their time efficiency; and it provides educators with a wide range of tests and assessments forms that help them in preparing tests and quizzes and also in calculating learners' final results.

2.2. Blended Learning and Language Skills

The basic goal of learning English is to master the four language skills to help the learner deal with real-life situations. These skills are: Listening, speaking, reading and writing. Many studies approved that Blended Learning approach help learners to improve their language skills.

Many studies have shown a great correlation between using online learning in the language classroom and a higher achievement in language skills proficiency. It is an effective way to improve foreign language skills.

Blended Learning provides interactive learning and encourages learners to communicate with their instructors and peers which improves their learning skills. Therefore, learners should be provided with the suitable language skills that will help them deal successfully with real-life situations.

Many studies have focused on how Blended Learning method affects the learners' four language integrated skills. In a study about using e-learning Moodle to develop EFL students' language skills, Soliman (2014) studied e-learning Moodle software, which was being used successfully in the British University in Egypt. It was concluded that Moodle enhanced students' language skills and independent learning. Similar results were found in a study about enhancing Students' Language Skills through Blended Learning, Banditvilai (2016) found that supplementing e-learning in teaching and learning English has many benefits. It helps to develop students' language skills better than in-class-only teaching, it encourages students to study independently and spend more time engaging in the English language to improve their language proficiency, it transfers the teaching process from being teacher-centred to student self-centred and it enables the learners to become more motivated and more involved in the learning process. Those results approved that Blended Learning helps teachers achieve several pedagogical goals, improves students' skills and improves teaching qualities.

Several studies discussed the approach of Blended Learning and its effect on the skills of language. The following two sections focus on some studies that discuss the role of Blended Learning in developing the four skills of English: listening, speaking, and reading, writing.

2.2.1. The Effects of Blended Learning on Listening and Speaking Skills

Listening and speaking are two primary fundamental skills in learning a language. They are considered significant parts of a learner's communication skills. Listening is the first step of communication. By listening, the learner receives the information, tries to explain, and understand it; then he moves to the other skill which is speaking. It is a receptive language skill while reading is considered a productive language skill. When using these two integrated skills, it will lead to a successful communication.

The review of literature revealed that Blended Learning has positive influence on the learners' acquisition of listening and speaking skills.

Several researches have studied the effect of Blended Learning on Listening and speaking skills. The association between Blended Learning and the students' achievements in the classroom has been investigated by several studies which result that successful implementation of Blended Learning in language learning may result in great improvement in students' skills. Moreover, the students show high satisfaction with the Blended Learning program.

Yang et al., (2013) investigated the use of Moodle in teaching listening and speaking. The study shown that when applying the approach of Blended Learning by using Moodle, learners

English speaking and listening as well as their critical thinking skills have improved significantly. Similarly, in a study about teaching public speaking by using Blended Learning method, Ibrahim & Yusoff (2013) have found that the approach of Blended Learning empowered the learners and provided them with more opportunities to practice speaking outside the classroom. In other words, Blended Learning approach helps learners to get the most benefits of their teacher from the classroom and at the same time they can learn at their own pace at home. Guangying (2014) who investigated the role of Blended Learning approach in improving listening and speaking skills. The study involved two groups of students: 59 students in each group. During the experiment, four standardised English language examinations were collected and statistically analysed. After the experiment, the results showed great progress in listening and speaking skills. Moreover, the study showed that the approach is effective in promoting teacher and student initiative and in enhancing learner autonomy.

In a study about using Blended Learning to develop Listening Skills, Caruso, Colombi & Tebbit (2017) implemented online listening quizzes in a course of English learning. A set of online listening quizzes was used. Around 100 learners were assessed. At the end of the course, the learners expressed that the online environment was flexible and the online helped in improving their skills of listening and their language proficiency. Those findings are compatible with what Aji

(2017) pointed out in a study about the implementation of Blended Learning in teaching Listening. The researcher experimented 28 students. Online listening materials and activities were used. An interview, observation and a questionnaire were used as the study instruments. The results of the study revealed that Blended Learning is an effective teaching method to develop the students' listening skill. It also influenced the students' speaking skill as well. Similarly, Rahmawati, (2019) studies using Blended Learning in a course of Listening and Speaking English. The experiment took place in a private university. The participants were English language major learners. In-class and online activities and materials were used. The online instruction was through Moodle web-based application. At the end of the experiment, learners perceived that applying the Blending Learning method in the listening and speaking course was very effective. Various interactive yet challenging learning materials and activities were used. They were relevant to the course syllabus. They lead to the improvement of learners' language skills.

By going through the previous literature, it can be noticed the positive effects of Blended Learning approach in enhancing the learners' performance in listening and speaking.

2.2.2. The Effects of Blended Learning on the Skills of Reading and Writing

Reading and writing are considered part language skills that should be mastered by the learner to achieve the ultimate goals of learning a language. The skill of reading is receptive language skill while writing is considered a productive language skill. Reading comprehension is defined as reading understanding that means that the learner should have the ability to comprehend the contents of a written text. Undoubtedly, the frequent access to the internet will encourage learners to read widely. Practising reading through the Internet, allows learners to move to a higher level of reading like, summing up and paraphrasing.

Several studies searched how Blended Learning affects the reading skill. Wahyuni, et al. (2014) have conducted using Blended Learning in teaching reading. The researchers applied The Blended Learning method on EFL learners to teach reading. The results showed that Blended Learning is an interactive teaching method that has improved learners' reading skills.

These results went parallel with what Zahedi & Tabatabaei (2015) found in their study about the effect of Blended Teaching on reading strategy used by Iranian EFL learners. 60 learners were divided into two groups. The results showed that Blended Learning method has positive effects on the learners' performance in reading.

In a study about using the social networking Edmodo in implementing Blended Learning to teach reading comprehension, Pratama (2015) experimented first-grade learners at West Java State University. The total number of students were 60 divided into two groups. Pre-test and post-test of reading comprehension, a set of questionnaire, observation and interview were used in the experiment. The study revealed that learners showed positive attitudes toward using Edmodo in teaching reading comprehension. Using Edmodo site enhanced the learners' interest and motivated them to learn reading comprehension successfully. Edmodo seems to facilitate reading comprehension skill and develop autonomous learning.

Another study that searched Blended Learning's effects on EFL learners' reading efficiency, by Ghazizadeh & Fatemipour (2017). The researchers selected 90 students divided into two groups for the experiment. The experimental group took additional lessons and tests. A language proficiency pre-test and a post-test were used. The findings revealed that Blended Learning has great effects on the learners' reading proficiency. Bataineh, & Mayyas (2017) applied the Blended Learning method by using Moodle site to search its effects on EFL reading and grammar. The results showed that Moodle was effective in improving learners' grammar and reading comprehension. The findings showed a great improvement in the skill of reading comprehension regarding the experimental group. These sub-skills of reading which are skimming and scanning help students to comprehend and deal with a specific text.

A new concept of results appeared in Kazakoff, Macaruso, & Hook (2018) study. The researchers have studied the efficiency using Blended Learning in elementary school reading instruction for students who are English learners. The researchers have designed an online program improve the skills of reading for slow learners. The study has revealed that the Blended Learning method has improved learners' comprehension of listening activities that were designed to develop learners' vocabulary story comprehending.

Similar results were found by Alnuari (2018) in a study about teaching reading comprehension by implementing Blended Learning method. The study experimented 20 second grade learners of senior high school. They were divided into two classes. The researcher has applied Pre-test and post-test on the learners. The study concluded that Blended Learning is an effective teaching method, and it leads to the improvement of learners' reading comprehension. The study showed that blended learning increased students' motivation and responsibility towards learning. These positive results could be a good solution for bored reading comprehension classes, since that teaching and learning reading is not an interesting process.

Other studies focused on the effect of Blended Learning on writing skills. Camahalan & Ruley (2014) searched the relationship between Blended Learning and teaching writing. Learners were given pre-assessment and post-assessment. The results revealed that learners showed more improvement in all writing assessments used throughout the study. Also, it was obvious that Blended Learning had a positive effect on most learners in this class and teachers would incorporate this learning tool in more of the writing lessons along with the reading curriculum.

Similar topic and results could be found in a study by Ghahari & Ameri-Golestan (2014) who has studied the impact of classroom teaching method and Blended learning method on Iranian EFL learners' writing performance. Two groups of EFL learners were set: a control group and an experimental group. The results revealed great development in students' writing performance. Also, it showed that a Blended Teaching method provided the learners with a more desirable condition that helped them improve their writing performance. Nearly all the mentioned studies have almost similar results that show the positive effects of Blended Learning on developing the writing skills.

In a study about using the e-mail to teach writing, Mabuan & Ebron (2017) found that using e-mails in academic writing may develop learners writing skills. Also, it can be used as social tool to help learners to engage, collaborate, with their peers. Collaboration, group work and pair work are very good techniques in practicing language activities and for improving problem-solving skills

In addition, more positive results could be found in a study by Milad (2017) who employed Web-Quests (WQs) to improve academic writing skills. 31 learners from the Academic Writing course have participated in questionnaires, pre-test, and post-test. The results showed that using blended learning had a great effect on improving the target learners' academic writing.

More studies could be found about the positive results of Blended Learning on the writing skills. In a study about using Blended Learning in improving English writing skills. Abdul Rahman, Azmi & Hassan (2020) have experimented a group of university learners in Malaysia. The findings have revealed that using Blended Learning in teaching writing, has improved learners' writing skills, self-esteem, and their interest in learning English writing. Clearly, Blended Learning creates interest in the class, improves students' language skills, leads to a deeper learning, motivates students, and at the same times makes them enthusiastic, active, and more involved in technology.

In another study about Blended Learning's impact on ESL reading and writing skills, Shaikh, Lohar & Shah (2020) found that this approach had a great impact on the participants. Moreover, it improved ESL skills of reading and writing. Also, the results showed that this approach provided the learners with other skills as well as subskills.

As seen from the results of the literature review, it has been approved that Blended Learning approach has positive effects in developing the English language competencies. The reviewed studies mentioned that Blended Learning could be used by educators as an educational approach to improve the learners' English language skills which are listening, speaking, reading and writing.

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

Blended Learning remains a relatively new concept at many academic institutions; however, most researches indicate that implementing a carefully-planned Blended Learning method will lead to a successful learning experience. Based on the results of the review of literature, it has been clear that Blended Learning approach contributes in motivating the learners to learn English. Different educational institutions around the world are heading to apply the Blended Learning approach in their educational system. There are some basic elements that ensures an effective language teaching and learning by using Blended Learning. The first element is the quality of the technology system in an institution. To establish a successful Blended Learning, a free, good quality of internet connections should be applied to provide efficiency,

reliability, and ease of navigation. Generally, it is recommended that in training courses user-friendly technology should be used, since educators and students do not need to practice high levels of technology in language courses.

The second element is related to the syllabus and the type of teaching platform used. The educational institutions need to upgrade the English language platform in a way that blends between face-to-face instruction and online instruction.

The third element is related to instructors. Language teachers are recommended to implement new methodology of Blended Learning to fulfil the requirements of learning in the new era of technology. To increase the effectiveness of Blended Teaching and Learning, instructors should improve their personal competences in technology skills and the implementation of ICT (Information and Communication Technology). Therefore, the educational institutions should provide instructors with methodologies and computer training courses. There is a strong need to use the latest computer, software, and internet technology by language instructors. The training courses should be around the year and should include all aspects related to this method: the ways to apply it, how to prepare the suitable material that could blend between the two instructions, its benefits, the challenges that may face the instructors and the learners and how to deal with those issues. Therefore, it is very important to train teachers how to use Blended Learning effectively in teaching English language. Therefore, it is important for educators to recognize how to use new technologies in ways to get the maximum benefits. They should be aware of the features of each method either face-to-face learning, online learning or Blended Learning to build specialized courses that meet learners' needs. The effectiveness of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) depends mainly on the teachers' motivation and the way it is used. Teachers should choose the suitable technological tool for each method of teaching. To have an effective Blended learning, it is recommended to engage teachers with a well-prepared pedagogic project.

The last element is related to the learners. Learners should possess at least basic computer skills before integrating in a Blended Learning course. Therefore, the educational institutions need to prepare training course for the learners to know how to deal with the educational online platforms. The success of the training courses either for designed for educators or for learners, is affected by their attitude towards using technology in teaching and learning, their skills in using technology and how easy dealing with online platforms.

4. CONCLUSION

Blended Learning is considered a new educational approach that is used in many institutions. It is a trend in the era of technological education. It approved to be a great method that fulfils several benefits. It is an effective method in improving the learners' capacity in learning English if it is implemented appropriately. Blended Learning is a valuable teaching method that leads to the achievement of the teaching goals successfully.

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the benefits of using Blended Learning approach on learning and teaching English. Many related studies have been reviewed to find out the effects of applying Blended Learning in teaching and learning English and specifically, the effect of this approach on acquiring the four integrated skills of English: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. This review approved that the method of Blended Learning has great effects English language acquisition. Sejdiu (2014) stated that the Blended Learning could be the most suitable teaching and learning approach for teachers and learners, since it enables the teachers to overcome the challenges in teaching English and at the same time it helps the learners to develop their language skills. Moreover, as it been mentioned that this approach combines face-to-face teaching and online teaching therefore, it helps learners to use the language constantly inside and outside the classroom. This facilitates the language learning process and improves the learners' performance in English.

When implementing high-quality Blended Learning program, it will provide a lot of benefits for learners, educators, and the whole educational system. A good Blended Learning program provides learners with skills including strong communication and collaboration skills, expertise in technology, innovative and creative thinking skills, and the skill of solving problems. With all these skills, the learner will be well-prepared for future job. Integrating technology with learning will encourage learners to search for information continuously. Excellent Blended Learning programs help in facilitating student's learning, improving interactive skills, and building interest in learning.

Blended Learning provides learners of English with great opportunities to deal with technology and gain varied skills to be ready for e-university, e-work, and e-life.

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